

CONDUCTING TYPES OF SUPERVISION IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract. *In this article, the professor-teacher who conducted training sessions on the relevant subject is prohibited from participating in the final type of control. Professors and teachers of other higher education institutions in the relevant subject may be involved in conducting the final type of supervision based on an agreement. The composition of the commission is formed from professors and teachers of relevant subjects and experts in the field. The assessment of students' knowledge is recorded by the professor-teacher of the relevant subject in the journal of students' mastery of subjects (hereinafter referred to as Journal). In addition, the professor-teacher can conduct the assessment of students' knowledge in the electronic system. The professor-teacher records the marks given to the student in the journal on the same day. If the assessment of the student's knowledge was carried out in the form of a written work, then the professor-teacher should record the results of the students in a journal within 3 days.*

Keywords: *modern, linguistics, mentalities, cultures, translation, versatility, traditions, concepts, different phenomena, complexity, sequence, similarity, relevance, inter-linguistic, international views.*

Assessment of students' knowledge is carried out in a 5-grade system. Conducting the intermediate control type and evaluating the student's knowledge on this type of control is carried out by the professor-teacher who conducted the training in the relevant subject. Conducting the final type of control and evaluating the student's knowledge in this type of control is carried out by a professor who did not conduct the training. A professor who has conducted training in the relevant subject is prohibited from participating in the final type of control. Professors and teachers of other higher education institutions in the relevant subject may be involved in conducting the final type of supervision based on an agreement. The composition of the commission is formed from professors and teachers of relevant subjects and experts in the field. Experts from other organizations may be involved in the commission based on agreement. The types of supervision in a higher educational institution are constantly studied by the educational quality control department of the relevant higher educational institution. In cases where it is determined that the procedure for conducting the types of control is violated, the results of the types of control conducted may be canceled and the corresponding type of control may be re-conducted. The student must have passed the intermediate control type before the final control type for the relevant subject. A student who did not pass the intermediate control type and was evaluated with a "2" (unsatisfactory) grade for this control type will not be included in the final control type. A student who is not included or not included in the final control type, as well as evaluated with a grade of "2" (unsatisfactory) according to this control type, is considered an academic debtor. If a student does not enter the intermediate and (or) final type of control for valid reasons, it is allowed to resubmit the corresponding type of control based on the order of the dean of the faculty.

Students with academic debt of 4 or more subjects are not allowed to retake and they are dropped from the course by order of the rector (head, branch director) of the higher education

institution. If the student fails to retake the intermediate and (or) final type of control the first time, a commission will be formed by the dean of the faculty. The composition of the commission is formed from professors and teachers of the relevant subject and experts in the field. The commission will conduct the second intermediate and (or) final control and evaluate the student. The assessment of students' knowledge is recorded by the professor-teacher of the relevant subject in the journal of students' mastery of subjects (hereinafter referred to as Journal). In addition, the professor-teacher can conduct the assessment of students' knowledge in the electronic system.

The professor-teacher records the marks given to the student in the journal on the same day. If the assessment of the student's knowledge was carried out in the form of a written work, then the professor-teacher should record the results of the students in the Journal within 3 days.

When the student's knowledge of the control type is evaluated with a grade of "3" (satisfactory) or "4" (good) or "5" (excellent), it is not allowed to retake the control type. In cases where the student did not participate without good reason at the time of the control type, "0" is written in the Journal. The journal is signed by the professor, the head of the department and the dean of the faculty who conducted training in the relevant subject and is kept in the dean's office. The dean of the faculty is responsible for keeping the magazine. When students' grades for the final control type are recorded in the Journal, they must also be recorded in the student's Gradebook on the same day. In cases where the student's knowledge is evaluated with a grade of "2" (unsatisfactory) according to the type of final inspection, or a mark of "0" is written in the Journal, this grade or mark is not recorded in the student's Grade Book. The dean of the faculty and the professor-teacher of the relevant subject are responsible for the timely, correct and complete maintenance of the magazine, as well as for not making unreasonable changes to the grades and other information in it. At the end of the corresponding academic year, the student who was evaluated with a grade of "3" (satisfactory) or "4" (good) or "5" (excellent) in the subjects of the working curriculum by the rector of the higher education institution will be transferred to the next course based on the order of the (supervisor, branch director). The evaluation results are regularly discussed at department meetings, faculty and higher education institution councils, and appropriate decisions are made. Comparative comparison of the evaluation system of students' learning in the higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the 5-point or 100-point system and the evaluation system used in the higher education system of advanced foreign countries, based on the tables in the appendix of this Regulation is done.

Table 1

Baholashni 5 baholik shkaladan 100 ballik shkalaga o'tkazish					
JADVALI					
5-point scale	100-point scale	5-point scale	100-point scale	5-point scale	100-point scale
5,00 — 4,96	100	4,30 — 4,26	86	3,60 — 3,56	72
4,95 — 4,91	99	4,25 — 4,21	85	3,55 — 3,51	71
4,90 — 4,86	98	4,20 — 4,16	84	3,50 — 3,46	70
4,85 — 4,81	97	4,15 — 4,11	83	3,45 — 3,41	69
4,80 — 4,76	96	4,10 — 4,06	82	3,40 — 3,36	68

4,75 — 4,71	95	4,05 — 4,01	81	3,35 — 3,31	67
4,70 — 4,66	94	4,00 — 3,96	80	3,30 — 3,26	66
4,65 — 4,61	93	3,95 — 3,91	79	3,25 — 3,21	65
4,60 — 4,56	92	3,90 — 3,86	78	3,20 — 3,16	64
4,55 — 4,51	91	3,85 — 3,81	77	3,15 — 3,11	63
4,50 — 4,46	90	3,80 — 3,76	76	3,10 — 3,06	62
4,45 — 4,41	89	3,75 — 3,71	75	3,05 — 3,01	61
4,40 — 4,36	88	3,70 — 3,66	74	3,00	60
4,35 — 4,31	87	3,65 — 3,61	73	less than 3.0	Less than 60

It is important to properly plan and conduct the supervision process, create effective criteria, choose the right assessment methods and communicate the results to students. Assessment of speech activity types and language aspects is divided into subjective and objective assessment types. In order to avoid subjectivity in the assessment of two types of speech activity (writing and speaking), the criteria should be correctly and effectively constructed. Criteria types such as Checklist, Holistic, Analytical, Primary Trait Rubric, Multi-Trait are used by the pedagogue based on the purpose of control to prevent subjectivity. - The concept of teacher's assessment activity was created in the 90s of the 20th century. But it is not an exaggeration to say that the activity of teachers' assessment started earlier than that.

In her works, V.V. Polikarpova divides the scientists who conducted research on teachers' assessment activities into two groups. The first group includes works from 90 years ago, and the second group includes later periods. When analyzing both groups, Polikarpova obtained the following results:

- concepts describing the teacher's activity;
- the purpose of the teacher's evaluation activity;
- functions of the teacher's evaluation activity;
- content and nature of teachers' evaluation activities during the educational process;
- object and subject of assessment;
- results of teachers' assessment activities.

The works of Yu.B.Zotov, V.V.Davidova, L.M.Fridman, and D.B.Elkonin can be included in the first group until the 90s of the 20th century. The theoretical analysis shows that the concepts of "assessment" and "teacher's evaluation activity" are mainly used in this study. Scientists believed that the main purpose of the teacher's evaluation activity is to evaluate the knowledge of each student on the subject and the final control.

Scientists distinguish the following as the main functions of assessment activities; educational, educational, diagnostic and controlling. According to scientists, assessment does not require independent activity from students in the educational process, it is a process that depends on teachers, which is equivalent to the gnostic activity of teachers. The evaluation activity of teachers is to control the acquired knowledge of students, as a result of which the acquired knowledge, skills and competencies of students are evaluated.

Sh. A. Amonashvili, Ye. D. Bozhovich, L. I. Bozhovich, G. Yu. Ksenzova, V. M. Polonsky, N. V. Seleznev and other scientists say that the process of knowledge assessment is an independent activity of teachers, that is, their professional activity. But this activity was called differently by different scientists. Sh.A. Amonashvili (late 80s) stated that the assessment is the result of the evaluation process and it is carried out by a person. Amonashvili defines assessment

as teaching students to independently evaluate their own learning progress. Among the evaluation functions, the scientist attaches great importance to the stimulus function. He stated that assessment is the greatest stimulator of increasing students' motivation in the educational process. During the evaluation process, the teacher should evaluate the quality of the formed and developed knowledge, skills, and abilities of the students, show ways to improve them, show what and how to do and what model to follow.

V. M. Polonsky (70s) defines the evaluation activity of teachers as a process of systematic assessment of knowledge. The scientist sees the essence of the evaluation process in the following components; to determine the purpose of education, to determine the control exercises that show the achievement of these goals, to determine the ways that show the result of control. According to Polonsky, the assessment of knowledge has educational, educational and control purposes. The scientist focuses on the educational function. The scientist also notes the existence of various objects of control. He noted that for some teachers, the object of evaluation is the evidential material acquired by students, for others, the ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice, and for others, the ability to apply this knowledge in performing new tasks. The result of teachers' evaluation process is the grade received by their students. Studies conducted after the 1990s fall into two groups; Research in the directions of general pedagogy and theory and methodology of education and upbringing. As a result of theoretical analysis, teachers' assessment activities have been studied in the following directions in recent years. The first; research direction related to the study of teachers' professional activities (N.V. Kuzmina, Ye.V. Piskunova, etc.). The second; research direction related to the study of professional pedagogical education of teachers (I.V. Jernov, V.A. Kozqrev, I.S. Lomakina, N.F. Radionova, etc.). The third direction; general education (G. Yu. Ksenzova, N. V. Seleznev.). At the same time, the teachers' evaluation activity was considered by the authors as an independent activity, a stage of professional pedagogical activity or a component of professional pedagogical activity. G. Yu. Ksenzova used the term teacher's evaluation activity in her research. According to him, the goal of the teacher's evaluation activity is to develop the ability of independent self-evaluation in students. When the scientist talks about the object of the assessment activity, he means the independent development of the student in the process of individual growth. Thus, the result of the teacher's assessment activity is the student's adequate self-assessment. The above examples show that today there are different views on teacher evaluation activities. Regardless of different views, there are factors that describe the essence of this activity. That is, assessment activities:

- is an integral part of professional pedagogical activity.
- is the teacher's professional duty.
- is an activity that develops the student as a person and self-evaluation.

Evaluation activities are part of the teacher's professional activity and stimulate the active activity of students. Today, the main goal of assessment is not only to evaluate the acquired knowledge in students, but also to develop self-assessment skills in them. In order to effectively conduct the evaluation process, teachers must have evaluation competence. We can include the following in assessment competence:

- assesment ob'ektini ajratish (nimani baholash);
- assesment ob'ektini qabul qilish kompetentsiyasi;
- assesment ob'ektini baholash mezoni bilan moslashtirish kompetentsiyasi;
- assesment turini tanlash kompetentsiyasi;

- assesment natijasini talabalarga e'lon qilish kompetentsiyasi.

Evaluating the achievements, acquired skills and qualifications in the educational process is one of the permanent tasks of pedagogues. Unfortunately, most teachers have difficulty or discomfort when it comes to performance evaluation. As a result, the previously used tests are reused without analysis. To see the results of the tests, it is necessary to analyze them statistically. The results of the analysis provide positive or negative information about the tested material, the process of mastering it, and the teacher's methodology. Based on this information, teachers are expected to plan their further work and evaluate their performance. Unfortunately, teachers today pay very little attention to this process. In order for the assessment process and results to be effective, teachers should have assessment competence, that is, they should have knowledge about its basis, the creation and use of assessment methods. Assessment competence not only improves student achievement, but also helps to evaluate the teaching process and increase students' motivation to study. It is well known that assessment plays an important role in teaching and learning. It helps teachers decide whether goals and objectives are appropriate or inappropriate.

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